

Perioperative Anesthetic Management in a Pediatric Patient with an Anterior Mediastinal Mass: A Case Report

Jessie Carolina Ávila Huertas*¹, Edwin de Jesús Varguez Salas², Acela Concepción Gonzalez Rodriguez²

¹ Third-year resident in the Department of Anesthesiology. Department of Anesthesiology. Health Services of Yucatán. “Dr. Agustín O’Horán” General Hospital, Merida. Faculty of Medicine, Autonomous University of Yucatan.

² Attending physician in the Department of Anesthesiology. Health Services of Yucatán. “Dr. Agustín O’Horán” General Hospital, Mérida.

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Anterior mediastinal masses in pediatric patients represent a significant anesthetic challenge due to the high risk of respiratory and cardiovascular collapse, particularly during anesthetic induction and major thoracic procedures. Available evidence is limited and is based mainly on case reports, highlighting the importance of documenting clinical experiences that contribute to the understanding and management of these conditions.

Case Presentation: We present the case of an 11-year-old female patient diagnosed with a large anterior mediastinal mass occupying the left hemithorax, with extension to the pulmonary vessels, associated with respiratory failure and recurrent pleural effusions. She underwent anterior sternotomy, left upper lobectomy, and tumor resection under balanced general anesthesia. The intraoperative period was complicated by massive hemorrhage, requiring activation of the massive transfusion protocol, advanced hemodynamic support, and prolonged invasive mechanical ventilation. In the immediate postoperative period, she developed severe hypoxemia and was admitted to the Pediatric Intensive Care Unit.

Intervention and Results: Anesthetic management was performed using balanced general anesthesia, preserving spontaneous ventilation during induction and delaying neuromuscular blockade until the start of surgery. Management included invasive monitoring, vasopressor support, lung-protective ventilation strategies, and activation of the massive transfusion protocol. The patient developed postoperative respiratory failure requiring admission to the Intensive Care Unit. No complications attributable to the anesthetic technique were documented.

Conclusion: This case highlights the need for an individualized and dynamic anesthetic approach in pediatric patients with mediastinal masses. It also underscores the additional challenges posed by emergency scenarios, in which a complete preoperative evaluation and access to advanced resources recommended in the literature are not always feasible. In this context, decision-making based on pathophysiology, adaptation to available resources, and multidisciplinary coordination are essential to optimize perioperative outcomes in high-risk patients.

KEYWORDS: Anterior mediastinal mass; pediatric anesthesia; thoracic surgery; massive hemorrhage; spontaneous ventilation; emergency surgery; high-risk anesthesia.

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CASE REPORT

An 11-year-3-month-old female patient of mixed ethnicity, originally from and residing in Belize, weighing 24 kg and measuring 142 cm in height, was evaluated. She had no psychosocial risk factors and limited access to highly specialized healthcare services. Family medical history was

unremarkable. Non-pathological personal history included an age-appropriate diet, exclusive breastfeeding during the first six months of life, adequate complementary feeding, a sedentary lifestyle appropriate for her school age, Christian religion, and no exposure to tobacco, alcohol, or other substances.

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Her pathological history was negative for chronic degenerative diseases, allergies, and substance abuse. During the current admission, she received transfusion of two packed red blood cell units for anemia and one unit of fresh frozen plasma due to prolonged coagulation times, without adverse reactions. Multiple thoracenteses and placement of central venous catheters under sedation were documented, without previous anesthetic complications.

The current illness began five months before the surgical procedure, with intermittent fever followed by recurrent respiratory infections unresponsive to outpatient treatment, progressing to productive cough, dorsal pain, and exertional dyspnea, later accompanied by chest tightness. She experienced multiple hospitalizations for recurrent pleural effusions, escalated antibiotic management, and progressive diagnostic studies. Tuberculosis was ruled out with a negative GeneXpert test. Initial histopathological evaluation reported a poorly differentiated malignant neoplasm with STAT6+ expression, compatible with solitary fibrous tumor. Chest computed tomography demonstrated a mass within the left pulmonary parenchyma measuring 11 cm × 9 cm × 15 cm, associated with pulmonary collapse, compression of the left pulmonary artery, and displacement of the heart, trachea, and mediastinal structures to the right. (Figure 1). Due to progressive respiratory deterioration and imminent risk of cardiovascular collapse, urgent surgical resection was scheduled, although transthoracic echocardiography could not be performed.

During comprehensive preanesthetic evaluation, the patient was conscious and responsive, with a Glasgow Coma Scale score of 15, temperature of 36.5 °C, mild pallor, afebrile status, and tachypnea. She remained in the left lateral decubitus position because of intolerance to the supine position and required supplemental oxygen through a humidification system (PURITAN FiO₂ 70%), maintaining oxygen saturation between 92–95% and respiratory rate >50 breaths/min. Airway evaluation revealed no predictors of difficult airway (Mallampati I, Sternomental Distance I, Patil-Aldrete I, adequate mouth opening, no limitation of cervical extension), patent nostrils, intact oral cavity, tongue size appropriate for age, mixed fixed dentition, and no visible masses in the face or neck. Chest examination showed asymmetric respiratory movements, absent breath sounds in the left hemithorax, and right basal hypoventilation with mild intercostal retractions. Cardiac auscultation revealed heart sounds displaced to the right and tachycardia without murmurs. The abdomen was soft and depressible without signs of abdominal involvement. Extremities were hypotrophic, with palpable peripheral pulses and adequate capillary refill. She carried a 7 Fr triple-lumen left femoral central venous catheter.

She was classified as ASA IV due to respiratory failure secondary to mediastinal pulmonary mass with recurrent pleural effusions and oxygen requirement. She was categorized as EIVB anesthetic-surgical risk, with elevated

respiratory and thromboembolic risk given the neoplastic pathology, inflammatory state, and prolonged immobility. Preoperative laboratory tests showed anemia (Hb 9.9 g/dL), leukocytosis (12,200/μL) with neutrophilia, thrombocytosis (500,000/μL), coagulation abnormalities with PT and aPTT prolongation >5 seconds, INR 1.62, elevated fibrinogen (616 mg/dL), sodium 134 mEq/L, potassium 3.41 mEq/L, serum calcium 8.3 mg/dL, magnesium 1.5 mg/dL, creatinine 0.2 mg/dL, and urea 12 mg/dL, findings compatible with coagulation abnormalities in the context of acute inflammatory response. A perioperative plan was established including fasting according to ASA guidelines, blood product crossmatching, and multidisciplinary coordination with pediatric surgery, pediatric oncology, and pediatric intensive care.

The surgical procedure consisted of anterior sternotomy, left upper lobectomy, and tumor excision, lasting approximately 8 hours under balanced general anesthesia. Given the extensive anterior mediastinal mass and respiratory compromise, there was high risk of ventilatory deterioration in the supine position during conventional induction. (Figure 2). Anesthetic induction was performed with prior preparation of airway rescue strategies and advanced support according to available institutional resources. Before induction, dexmedetomidine infusion was initiated at 0.8–1.2 mcg/kg/h to achieve a plasma concentration of 0.3 mcg/mL. During induction, fentanyl 75 mcg IV, lidocaine 30 mg IV, propofol 40 mg IV, and sevoflurane (MAC 0.5) were administered. After ensuring effective spontaneous ventilation and hemodynamic stability, orotracheal intubation was performed using videolaryngoscopy (POGO 100%) with a reinforced 6.0 endotracheal tube fixed at 20 cm at the lip commissure, without difficulty. Prior to the beginning of surgery, fresh frozen plasma and tranexamic acid (15 mg/kg IV bolus followed by infusion at 1 mg/kg/h) were administered.

Anesthetic maintenance included sufentanil (0.3–0.5 mcg/kg/h), magnesium sulfate (5–10 mg/kg/h), sevoflurane 1–1.5 vol% (MAC 0.5–0.8), O₂ at 3 L/min with FiO₂ 70–98%, and vecuronium; neuromuscular blockade was initiated at the start of surgery and maintained with intermittent boluses for a total dose of 8 mg IV. Pressure-controlled mechanical ventilation with lung-protective strategy was used, with initial inspiratory pressure of 19 cmH₂O and PEEP of 5 cmH₂O, later adjusted to a maximum PEEP of 7 cmH₂O to maintain tidal volumes of 6–7 mL/kg predicted body weight. Hemodynamic support with norepinephrine, vasopressin, and epinephrine was required. Normothermia was maintained using a warming mattress and forced-air warming system; however, adequate control of operating room ambient temperature was not possible. Standard ASA monitoring included continuous electrocardiography, pulse oximetry, noninvasive blood pressure, capnography, and temperature monitoring. Invasive monitoring was additionally performed with ultrasound-guided placement of a right radial arterial

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line using a 22G catheter under sterile technique. This access allowed evaluation of pulse pressure variation for advanced hemodynamic management optimization. Processed electroencephalographic monitoring (SedLine) was also incorporated to assess anesthetic depth.

During the intraoperative period, massive bleeding estimated at 2000 mL was documented, prompting activation of the massive transfusion protocol with administration of packed red blood cells, fresh frozen plasma, and platelet apheresis. Approximately 3100 mL of fluids were administered, guided by pulse pressure variation (PPV <12%) and serial blood gas analyses, with intraoperative urine output of 620 mL (3.2 mL/kg/h). No transfusion reactions or major anesthetic adverse events were documented. At the end of the procedure,

the patient developed severe hypoxemia and hypercapnia; therefore, invasive mechanical ventilation was maintained, and she was transferred to the Pediatric Intensive Care Unit under deep sedation and dual vasopressor support for hypovolemic shock. No late anesthetic complications attributable to the technique or drugs used were identified. Anesthetic interventions were carried out according to available institutional resources, without major drug-related adverse reactions other than massive surgical bleeding. Immediate postoperative evolution was critical, with guarded prognosis, requiring close monitoring and continuous communication with family members. Definitive histopathological examination obtained six weeks later confirmed the diagnosis of Hodgkin lymphoma.

Figure 1. Chest computed tomography demonstrating a large left pulmonary-mediastinal mass with significant mass effect.

Figure 2. Surgically resected pulmonary mass.

DISCUSSION

The anesthetic management of anterior mediastinal masses in pediatric patients represents a high-risk clinical scenario because of the possibility of respiratory and cardiovascular collapse secondary to compression of critical intrathoracic structures. In this context, the present case is discussed in relation to the available evidence, emphasizing that thorough preoperative evaluation, appropriate risk stratification, and individualized anesthetic planning constitute fundamental pillars of perioperative management.^{2, 6, 8}

The patient described presented multiple predictors of high risk, including dyspnea, orthopnea, recurrent pleural effusions, and significant mediastinal shift, findings consistently associated with increased perioperative morbidity and mortality. In accordance with the literature, preservation of spontaneous ventilation during anesthetic induction was prioritized, allowing airway management under more stable physiological conditions.⁵ This approach

has been widely recommended in patients with significant mediastinal compression, since loss of muscle tone and early institution of positive-pressure ventilation may precipitate airway collapse.

Rudingwa et al. described a pediatric case in which positive-pressure ventilation and neuromuscular relaxation were associated with ventilatory deterioration, whereas spontaneous ventilation improved oxygenation and respiratory mechanics.⁵ In contrast, in our patient, although spontaneous ventilation was maintained during induction, a controlled transition to positive-pressure ventilation and delayed neuromuscular blockade was achieved without immediate airway collapse. This difference may be explained by the absence of significant tracheal obstruction in our case, with only airway displacement documented, highlighting the importance of preoperative anatomical evaluation in guiding anesthetic strategy.

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Similarly, Tan et al. reported a high incidence of perioperative complications in patients with mediastinal masses, including ventilatory failure and cardiovascular instability, regardless of the anesthetic technique employed.⁴ Our case supports this observation, since despite a carefully planned anesthetic strategy, perioperative evolution was mainly determined by tumor extension and surgical complexity. In particular, significant pulmonary involvement and extensive surgical manipulation contributed to progressive deterioration of gas exchange.

During the surgical phase, pressure-controlled mechanical ventilation under a lung-protective strategy was employed, with dynamic adjustment of ventilatory parameters according to the different surgical stages. Unlike scenarios in which positive-pressure ventilation is recommended to be avoided, in this case its use was necessary and initially safe because of the absence of critical tracheal obstruction and the need for surgical immobility given the tumor proximity to major vascular structures. This approach allowed adaptation to the different phases of the procedure, including sternotomy, tumor resection, lobectomy, and management of massive bleeding. However, the unfavorable respiratory evolution observed suggests that, even with protective ventilatory strategies, the interaction among pulmonary compression, ventilation/perfusion mismatch, and surgical injury may lead to progressive deterioration, as described in the literature.^{4,7}

In this regard, Blank and de Souza emphasize that combined compression of the airway and pulmonary vascular structures may produce severe ventilation/perfusion mismatch even in the absence of complete tracheal obstruction, contributing to the complexity of anesthetic management in these patients.⁹ This concept is particularly relevant in our case, where tumor proximity to the pulmonary artery likely played an important role in the deterioration of gas exchange.

Adam et al. described the anesthetic management of a pediatric patient with mediastinal mass in whom multidisciplinary planning allowed implementation of preoperative strategies aimed at reducing perioperative risk, including interventions that reduced compressive burden before the definitive procedure.⁶ This approach favored a more stable evolution during anesthetic induction and throughout the perioperative period. In contrast, in our case, rapid clinical progression and the anatomical extent of the lesion, with significant pulmonary involvement and proximity to major vascular structures, limited the possibility of less invasive prior interventions. As a result, it was necessary to proceed directly to major surgery in a high-risk context. This comparison highlights that although multidisciplinary planning is a key element, the feasibility of preoperative strategies largely depends on clinical presentation and tumor anatomy, which decisively influence perioperative evolution.

Tani et al., in their review of large anterior mediastinal tumors, proposed that beyond the mechanical risk of compression, these lesions generate a dynamic

pathophysiological environment in which small changes in ventilation, positioning, or anesthesia may trigger sudden cardiorespiratory deterioration, constituting the so-called mediastinal mass syndrome.⁷ From this perspective, the anesthetic challenge lies not only in identifying risk, but also in the ability to anticipate its behavior throughout the different phases of the procedure. In our case, this dynamic interaction was particularly evident, since despite structured anesthetic planning and the absence of critical tracheal obstruction, the combination of pulmonary compromise, vascular compression, and surgical manipulation resulted in progressive deterioration of gas exchange. This finding reinforces the notion that initial stability does not exclude the possibility of subsequent decompensation and underscores the need for continuous vigilance and a real-time adaptable anesthetic strategy.

A particularly relevant element in this case was the presence of massive intraoperative bleeding, which added a critical hemodynamic component to the already elevated respiratory risk. Prompt activation of the massive transfusion protocol, use of antifibrinolytics, vasopressor support, and advanced hemodynamic monitoring were decisive for intraoperative management. Nevertheless, the patient developed postoperative respiratory failure, reflecting the combined impact of previous pulmonary compromise and the magnitude of the surgical procedure.

Importantly, no complications directly attributable to the anesthetic technique or medications used were documented, suggesting that the outcome was primarily determined by the disease pathophysiology and surgical complexity, reflecting the unstable physiological state in which the interaction among pulmonary compression, vascular compromise, and anesthesia- and surgery-induced changes may unpredictably alter cardiorespiratory dynamics, even in initially stable patients.

Furthermore, the definitive diagnosis of Hodgkin lymphoma highlights the possible discrepancy between initial histopathological findings and the final diagnosis in complex mediastinal masses. This aspect has important clinical implications because it may influence major therapeutic decisions, including the indication for surgery. In this sense, anesthesiologists may face scenarios in which perioperative management requires decision-making under diagnostic uncertainty, adding another level of complexity to anesthetic risk and multidisciplinary planning.

Overall, this case underscores that anesthetic management in pediatric patients with mediastinal masses must be dynamic, flexible, and focused on anticipating critical events. Preservation of spontaneous ventilation during induction, delayed neuromuscular blockade, and controlled transition to positive-pressure ventilation according to surgical requirements represent complementary strategies within an individualized approach. Among the main strengths of this report is the implementation of a highly individualized anesthetic strategy in a setting with significant resource

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limitations, requiring decision-making based on pathophysiology and immediate clinical assessment. Despite the urgent nature of the procedure, conditioned by imminent risk of cardiorespiratory collapse and the impossibility of performing complete preoperative evaluation — including transthoracic echocardiography — a sequential anesthetic strategy aimed at minimizing risks was successfully established. Preservation of spontaneous ventilation during induction, followed by a controlled transition to mechanical ventilation adapted to surgical requirements, reflects dynamic real-time planning. Likewise, the use of available monitoring and close surveillance allowed early identification and timely management of major complications such as massive bleeding and hemodynamic instability, while effective coordination among anesthesiology, surgery, and intensive care teams was essential for intraoperative decision-making and continuity of care. Nevertheless, this report has inherent limitations, including its single-case nature, which restricts generalization of findings, as well as emergency conditions and limited resource availability — such as absence of extracorporeal support, fiberoptic bronchoscope, and selective ventilation devices — which limited implementation of some advanced strategies described in the literature. However, these circumstances reflect frequent scenarios in clinical practice and underscore the importance of adapting anesthetic management to available resources without compromising patient safety.

CONCLUSION

The anesthetic management of pediatric patients with anterior mediastinal masses constitutes a highly complex clinical challenge in which the risk of cardiorespiratory collapse may vary dynamically throughout the perioperative period. This case demonstrates that the anesthetic strategy must be individualized and adaptable, based on integration of clinical and imaging findings as well as understanding of the underlying pathophysiology.

Preservation of spontaneous ventilation during induction, followed by a controlled transition to positive-pressure ventilation and neuromuscular blockade according to surgical requirements, may represent a safe alternative in patients without critical tracheal obstruction, allowing a balance between respiratory stability and operative needs. However, perioperative evolution may be mainly determined by tumor extension, pulmonary and vascular involvement, and the magnitude of the surgical procedure, beyond the anesthetic technique employed.

Likewise, this report highlights that in emergency scenarios and resource-limited settings, effective anesthetic strategies may still be implemented through pathophysiology-based decision-making and close monitoring, even in the absence of advanced tools. Variability in clinical behavior, the possibility of delayed deterioration, and the diagnostic uncertainty associated with these entities underscore the need

for a continuous multidisciplinary approach and high intraoperative adaptability.

Finally, this case contributes to the literature by demonstrating that successful anesthetic management in pediatric mediastinal masses depends not only on technological availability, but also on anticipation of critical scenarios, flexibility of strategy, and effective integration of the healthcare team.

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Conflict of Interest

None.

Ethical Considerations

The patient’s mother was informed at all times about the diagnosis, the interventions performed, and the potential risks. Written informed consent was obtained for the surgical and anesthetic procedures, as well as for publication of this case report, in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and the institutional regulations of the hospital

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